

Aqueous hydrogen peroxide activated by ammonium heptamolybdate catalyst – A mild clean effective reagent system for the deprotection of oximes, semicarbazones and phenylhydrazones at room temperature

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Abstract : Oximes, phenylhydrazones and semicarbazones of a wide variety of aldehydes and ketones are cleanly cleaved to the corresponding carbonyl compounds in good to acceptable yields using environmentally safe and convenient oxidizer, 30% hydrogen peroxide in catalytic combination with 20 mol% ammonium heptamolybdate in aqueous acetic acid or tetrahydrofuran at room temperature. Absence of overoxidized by-products in case of oxidation-prone aromatic aldehydes, α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and compatibility with various common functional groups such as hydroxy, methoxy, epoxy, amino, methylenedioxy, conjugated and unconjugated C=C bonds are some of the key advantageous features of the method.

Keywords : Deprotection, oximes, semicarbazones, phenylhydrazones, 30% hydrogen peroxide, ammonium heptamolybdate.

Introduction

Oximes, phenylhydrazones and semicarbazones constitute a class of imines that are extensively utilized for protection, characterization and isolation of carbonyl compounds¹. Regeneration of carbonyl compounds from these carbonyl precursors has engaged considerable attention of organic chemists over the years² in view of the prime importance of functional group transformations involving aldehydes and ketones in multistep organic syntheses. Apart from their importance as latent protected forms of carbonyl groups, deprotection of oximes assumes special importance because their synthesis from non-carbonyl sources such as nitroalkanes, imines, carboxamides by way of Beckmann rearrangement, the Nef reaction, the Barton reaction, the amination of active methylene compounds via nitrosation and reduction offers useful entry to carbonyl compounds^{3,4}. Therefore, it is not surprising that deoxygenation protocols have evoked considerable contemporary interest and scant attention has been paid to development of general methods of cleavage of this class of derivatives. Only a few reports^{3d-f} are available that deal with the cleavage of these imines in a general way. A good number of deoxygenation methods documented in literature involve reagents that are used in excess amounts or toxic and not readily available⁵⁻⁸. Many

of the effective hydrolytic and oxidative methods developed for this purpose are either chemoselective for ketoximes or not mild enough for aldioximes and oxidation-prone polyfunctional substrates. Currently, green chemistry issues have been addressed to in newer deoxygenation approaches utilizing photosensitizers, non-toxic catalytic amount of reagents, particularly in aqueous medium. Thus, cleavage of oximes has been accomplished with chloranil/ $h\nu$ ⁹, platinum(II)terpyridyl acetylacetonate complex¹⁰, catalytic combination of I_2 with SDS in aqueous medium¹¹, silicon bromide on wet silica gel¹², iodic acid¹³, 2,2'-dipyridyl diselenide with triphenylphosphine¹⁴, 2-iodylbenzoic acid in the presence of β -cyclodextrin catalyst¹⁵, iodoxybenzoic acid¹⁶, glyoxylic acid¹⁷, functional ionic liquids physically confined in silica gel¹⁸ and chloramine T¹⁹. Our continuing interest in developing oxidative protection methods utilizing peroxides²⁰ prompted us to explore aqueous hydrogen peroxide in combination with catalytic amount of ammonium heptamolybdate as a deoxygenating agent. A diluted aqueous solution of hydrogen peroxide is an inexpensive, convenient, safe and environmentally compatible oxidizer because of its high oxygen content and generation of water as the only reduction product. However, oxidations of organic compounds with hydrogen peroxide are usually kinetically slow in absence of a suitable catalytic activa-

tor. A host of early transition metal compounds, particularly those of V, Ti, Mo and W, have been utilized for this purpose^{21,22}. Ammonium heptamolybdate is a commercially available, cheap reagent that seemed to us an attractive candidate for activation of hydrogen peroxide particularly because oxidations with hydrogen peroxide catalyzed by Mo^{VI} have been reported to occur effectively at higher pH (5–7) compared to similar V^V-catalyzed reactions²³, and, therefore, more tolerable for acid-sensitive organic substrates. Thus, oxidation of alcohols to corresponding carbonyl compounds has been accomplished with hydrogen peroxide in the presence of ammonium heptamolybdate catalyst and potassium carbonate²⁴. We report herein deprotection of a wide range of oximes, semicarbazones and phenylhydrazones using hydrogen peroxide as the terminal oxidant along with ammonium heptamolybdate catalyst in aqueous acetic acid and tetrahydrofuran.

We surmised that benzaldehyde oxime **1** could serve as a representative aromatic aldoxime for optimization of reactions conditions because of propensity of benzalde-

hyde released upon deoxygenation towards further oxidation and therefore cleavage of **1** would give us a good feel of mildness of the oxidizing system. The result of optimization experiments are summarized in Table 1.

The initial exploratory experiments thus clearly demonstrated that cleavage of **1** was not feasible with this reagent system in water as the reaction medium, with or without sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), unless an organic co-solvent is used. Therefore, surfactant-promoted micelle formation¹¹ route to circumvent the problem associated with poor solubility of the substrate did not work in this case. Use of 2 ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide per mmol of substrate along with 20 mol% of ammonium heptamolybdate in aqueous tetrahydrofuran or acetic acid gave excellent yield of **2** without overoxidation. However, the yield was marginally better in acetic acid (1 : 1 v/v). The optimized reaction condition worked well for oximes of a wide array of aromatics aldehydes and ketones, cyclic ketones and α,β -unsaturated ketones (Table 2).

Thorough resistance of acetophenone oxime O-methyl ether (entry 15) towards deoxygenation even upon prolonged exposure (48 h) suggests crucial involvement of oximic hydroxy group in the cleavage process. An intermediate **3**, analogous to peroxyoxymolybdenum(VI) alkoxide species in case of oxidation of secondary alcohols to ketones²⁴, is tentatively suggested. However, oxidation of alcohols is subject to rate acceleration in the presence of base which is consistent with abstraction of an activated

Table 1. Cleavage of benzaldehyde oxime **1** with 30% H₂O₂ and ammonium heptamolybdate catalyst

Entry	30% H ₂ O ₂ , (NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O THF/CH ₃ CO ₂ H-H ₂ O, rt		PhCHO 2 Solvent	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%) of 2
	PhCH=NOH 1 30% H ₂ O ₂ (ml)	Ammonium heptamolybdate (mol%)			
1	1	10	THF-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	8	55
2	1	10	H ₂ O	20	No change
3	1	10	H ₂ O, SDS (0.1 M in 5 ml H ₂ O)	24	No change
4	2	10	THF-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	7	58
5	2	20	THF-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	5	86
6	2	20	CH ₃ COOH-H ₂ O (1 : 1)	5	90

Table 2. Deoxygenation with 30% hydrogen peroxide and ammonium heptamolybdate catalyst at room temperature

Entry	Substrate	Reaction time (h)	Yield of corresponding carbonyl compound ^a (%)			
1	PhCH=NOH	(i) 5 (ii) 5	86 90	13		(i) 10 70
2		(i) 6 80				
3		(i) 48 (ii) 48 No change No change				
4		(i) 8 80				
5		(i) 16 (ii) 15	85 88	(i) Reactions conditions : 30% hydrogen peroxide (2 ml per mmol of substrate), 20 mol% ammonium heptamolybdate, THF-H ₂ O (1 : 1 v/v), rt.		
6		(i) 20 (ii) 20	68 75	(ii) Reactions conditions : 30% hydrogen peroxide (2 ml per mmol of substrate), 20 mol% ammonium heptamolybdate, CH ₃ COOH-H ₂ O (1: 1 v/v), rt.		
7		(i) 12 (ii) 12	65 70	^a Yields refer to products isolated by column chromatography.		
8		(i) 24 (ii) 24	60 65	C-H by base. In contrast, no significant change in rate of deoxygenation of benzaldehyde oxime 1 was observed upon addition of 10 mol% of potassium carbonate to the reaction mixture in THF-H ₂ O. Intramolecular transfer of hydroxyl group from a hydroperoxy moiety through a cyclic transition state to C=N of the initially formed putative peroxy species 3 leading to its cleavage seems likely (Scheme 1).		
9		(i) 10 (ii) 8	73 78	A hypothetical alternative mechanism may be also proposed that involves electrophilic epoxidation of carbon-nitrogen double bond of oxime to give the unstable oxaziridine species 3a. Subsequent hydrolytic cleavage of 3a generates the carbonyl compound (Scheme 2).		
10		(i) 12 (ii) 10	75 84	Encouraged by the potential of this oxidant system to regenerate carbonyl compounds from oximes we set out to evaluate its efficacy for deprotection of semicarbazones and phenylhydrazones. Some representative semicarbazones of aromatic aldehydes and ketones with varying reactivity levels such as benzaldehyde, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde, 2,3-		
11		(i) 1 (ii) 1	95 98			
12		(i) 15	85			

methylenedioxybenzaldehyde, acetophenone, benzophenone as well as cyclopentanone semicarbazone were subjected to essentially identical reaction conditions used for deoxygenation. Deblocking was generally much slower in these cases in aqueous tetrahydrofuran. However, the cleavage of semicarbazones was much faster with 0.2 mol equivalent of ammonium heptamolybdate along with 2 ml of 30% H_2O_2 per mmol of substrate in aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1 v/v). Phenylhydrazones (entries 8–11, Table 3) were found to be comparatively less reluctant towards cleavage in both solvent systems used. The results of these experiments are summarized in Table 3.

To summarize, 30% hydrogen peroxide in catalytic combination with 20 mol% ammonium heptamolybdate in aqueous tetrahydrofuran/acetic acid constitutes a reagent system for cleavage of carbon-nitrogen double bond of oximes, semicarbazones and phenylhydrazones at room temperature. The method is based on cost-effective, environmentally compatible reagents and operationally simple. Compatibility with a large number of functional groups such as phenolic hydroxy, methoxy, epoxy, conjugated as well as unconjugated carbon-carbon double bonds and absence of overoxidized products particularly for aromatic aldoximes are the key advantageous features of this protocol.

Table 3. Regeneration of carbonyl compounds from semicarbazones and phenyl hydrazones with 30% H_2O_2 and catalytic amount of ammonium heptamolybdate

Entry	Substrate	Reaction time (h)	Yield of corresponding carbonyl compound ^a (%)
1		(i) 10	55
		(ii) 6	85
2		(i) 17	45
		(ii) 10	80
3		(i) 8	45
		(ii) 5	78
4		(i) 6	70
		(ii) 1.5	95
5		(i) 17	48
		(ii) 10	82

Table-3 (contd.)

6		(i) 10	65
		(ii) 6	88
7		(i) 12	48
		(ii) 4	85
8		(i) 3	58
		(ii) 2	92
9		(i) 6	70
		(ii) 3	86
10		(i) 6	70
		(ii) 4	86
11		(i) 8	64
		(ii) 6	90

^aIsolated yield upon column chromatography; products were characterized by spectral data (FT-IR, ¹H NMR) and comparison with authentic sample (superimposable IR, mixed m.p.).

(i) Refers to reaction conditions : 30% H₂O₂ (2 ml), ammonium heptamolybdate (20 mol% per mmol of substrate) in THF-H₂O (1 : 1 v/v), rt.

(ii) Refers to reaction conditions : 30% H₂O₂ (2 ml), ammonium heptamolybdate (20 mol% per mmol of substrate) in CH₃COOH-H₂O (1 : 1 v/v), rt.

Experimental

30% Hydrogen peroxide and ammonium heptamolybdate tetrahydrate, (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O were procured from E. Merck, India and used as such. Oximes, semicarbazones and phenylhydrazones were prepared by standard literature procedures²⁵. The *E,Z*-isomers of the oximes were not separated, unless stated. Solvents used for experiments and chromatographic purifications were used without further purification. Silica gel (60–120 mesh, Spectrochem, India) was used for chromatographic experiments.

Representative procedure for regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes with 30% H₂O₂ in the presence of ammonium heptamolybdate catalyst :

To a well-stirred solution of benzaldehyde oxime (508 mg, 4.2 mmol) in acetic acid-water (1 : 1 v/v, 3 ml) was added 30% hydrogen peroxide (8.5 ml) and then ammonium heptamolybdate (1030 mg, 0.835 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 h (with TLC-monitoring). The reaction mixture was diluted with water (20 ml) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 ml). The combined organic extract was washed successively with ferrous sulphate solution (2 × 3 ml), saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (3 × 5 ml), water (2 × 3 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue left after concentration of solvent was chromatographed over silica gel using light petrol as eluent to furnish benzaldehyde (400 mg, 90%). Its identity was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample (TLC, superimposable IR).

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References

1. S. R. Sandler and W. Karo, "Organic Functional Group Preparations", Academic Press, London, 1989, 430.
2. (a) T. W. Greene and P. G. M. Wuts, "Protective Groups in Organic Synthesis", 3rd ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1991, pp. 352-359; (b) A. Corsaro, U. Chiacchia and V. Pistara, *Synthesis*, 2001, 1903.
3. (a) G. W. Kabalka, R. D. Pace and P. P. Wadgaonkar, *Synth. Commun.*, 1990, **20**, 2453; (b) R. C. Larock, "Comprehensive Organic Transformations", Wiley-VCH, New York, 1999, 1277; (c) D. H. R. Barton, J. M. Beaton, L. E. Geller and M. M. Pecket, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4076; (d) D. H. R. Barton, D. J. Lester and S. V. J. Ley, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 276; (e) *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1980, 276; (f) F. Shirini, M. A. Zolfigol, M. Khaleghi and I. Mohammadpour-Baltork, *Synth. Commun.*, 2003, **33**, 1839 and references cited therein.
4. A. Coma, P. Serna and H. Garcia, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 6358.
5. R. S. Varma and H. M. Meshram, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 5427.

6. A. Boruah, B. Baruah, D. Prajapati and J. S. Sandhu, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 4267.
7. D. Enders, H. Elchenauer, U. Babus, H. Schubert and K. A. M. Kermer, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, **40**, 1345.
8. G. A. Olah, M. Arvanaghi and G. K. Suryaprakash, *Synthesis*, 1980, 220.
9. H. J. P. Lijser, F. H. Fardoun, J. R. Sawyer and M. Quant, *Org. Lett.*, 2002, **4**, 2325.
10. Y. Yang, D. Zhang, L.-Z. Wu, B. Chem, L.-P. Zhang and C.-H. Tung, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **69**, 4788.
11. P. Gogai, P. Hazrika and D. Konwar, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, **70**, 1934.
12. S. K. De, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 9055.
13. S. Chandrasekhar and K. Gopalaiah, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 4023.
14. M. Martin, G. Marti'nez, F. Urpi' and J. Vilarrasa, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 5559.
15. N. S. Krishnaveni, K. Surendra, Y. V. D. Nageshwar and K. R. Rao, *Synthesis*, 2003, 1968.
16. D. S. Bose and P. Srinivas, *Synlett.*, 1998, 977.
17. S. P. Chavan and P. Soni, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 3161.
18. D. Li, F. Shi, S. Guo and Y. Deng, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 265.
19. K. P. Gupta, L. Manral and K. Ganeshan, *Synthesis*, 2007, 1390.
20. (a) N. C. Ganguly and M. Datta, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 2005, 218; (b) *Synlett.*, 2004, 659; (c) N. C. Ganguly, M. Datta and P. De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 308.
21. G.-J. ten Brink, I. W. C. E. Arends and R. A. Sheldon, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 4105.
22. B. S. Lane and K. Burgess, *Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **103**, 2457.
23. (a) M. Bhattecharjee and J. Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1995, 238; (b) J. Shina, S. Layek, G. C. Mandal and M. Bhattecharjee, *Chem. Commun.*, 2001, 1916.
24. B. M. Trost and Y. Masuyama, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, **25**, 173.
25. A. I. Vogel, "A Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., ELBS and Longman Group Ltd., London, 1973.